

Rheological Properties of Some Binary Organic Systems

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The viscosities and activation energies for the binary naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene and naphthalenediphenylamine eutectic melts were found to be more than pure components and off-eutectic mixtures. This is explained on the basis of microregions rich in one or the other component. In naphthalene-thymol system viscosity at eutectic shows a decrease, whereas activation energy shows an increase in passing from one component to the other. This decrease is attributed to the breaking of hydrogen bonds in thymol molecule. Strength of interaction in these binary systems as obtained from viscosities of mixing shows a weak interaction in all the three systems.

VISCOSITY measurements have turned out to be an effective tool to investigate the structure of liquids. Pluss¹, Fisher *et al.*² and Jones *et al.*³ have observed anomalously low viscosities of molten Pb-Sn at eutectic composition. Dutchak and Panasyuk⁴ found that the kinematic viscosity of Bi-Sb alloys followed the exponential form. Wilson⁵ pointed out that many systems exhibited a sharp minimum in viscosity at eutectic composition in both Pb-Sn and Pb-Sb melts that could not be found by Gebhardt *et al.*⁶ The viscosity of Pu-Fe eutectic alloy has been measured as a function of temperature by Jones *et al.*⁷ Higher activation energy for viscous flow than their pure components has been reported.

In view of the anomalous behaviour of viscosities in binary systems, the work on the viscosities of certain binary organic systems giving faceted-faceted crystal morphologies was undertaken. The studies on the viscosities of naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene, naphthalene-thymol and naphthalene-diphenylamine are presented in this paper.

Experimental

Naphthalene (B.D.H.) was purified by ordinary distillation followed by slow sublimation in a china dish at 233 K. *p*-Dichlorobenzene (B.D.H.) was purified by repeated distillation and the distillate was collected at 447-451 K under normal pressure. Diphenylamine (E. Merck, A.R.) was distilled under a pressure 22 mm at 452 K. Thymol (Schering, A.G.) was purified by repeated crystallization with absolute ethanol and kept in a vacuum desiccator for about a week. The melting points of purified materials, *i.e.* naphthalene (353.3 K), *p*-dichlorobenzene (326.7 K), diphenylamine (326.4 K) and thymol (322.8 K) are in good agreement with the literature values.

Determination of viscosity: Viscosities of mixtures and pure components were determined at various

temperatures near their melting points. For this purpose, a modified Ostwald's viscometer was used to note the time of flow for a given volume, which was kept constant in each case and gave fairly good results when the kinetic energy correction was applied. The accuracy was verified using a liquid of known viscosity and density at different temperatures. Specific gravity bottles with fine capillaries were used to find the densities in the molten state at the same temperatures. All the measurements were made in a thermostat (accuracy $\pm 0.05^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

Viscosity measurements are important in elucidating the nature of the liquid eutectic. Such studies can throw much light on the state of aggregation in the liquid and the presence of any type of specific interactions.

The viscosities of naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene, naphthalene-diphenylamine and naphthalene-thymol systems over the whole range of compositions at different temperatures were determined. There was a decrease in viscosities with the rise in temperature for pure components, as well as, their mixtures. Viscosities were determined at 353 K (m.p. of naphthalene) and at lower temperatures. The viscosities at 353 K are given in Table 1. There is a decrease in the viscosities at 353 K in naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene system, whereas an increase in the viscosities at 353 K for the systems naphthalene-thymol and naphthalene-diphenylamine is observed (Table 1). Fig. 1 represents the curves of viscosities (η) at 353 K against mole fraction of naphthalene for the three binary systems. It is evident that when one component is added to the other, the viscosity of the mixture rises and falls gradually for naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene and naphthalene-diphenylamine systems, respectively. But at the eutectic composition, there is a sudden increase in the value of viscosity as indicated by the

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TABLE 1—VISCOSITIES AND ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR VISCOSITIES OF SYSTEMS AT 353 K

Naphthalene- <i>p</i> -dichlorobenzene			Naphthalene-thymol			Naphthalene-diphenylamine		
Mole fraction of <i>p</i> -dichlorobenzene	η (cp)	$E_{vis} \times 10^{-3}$ cal mol ⁻¹	Mole fraction of thymol	η (cp)	$E_{vis} \times 10^{-3}$ cal mol ⁻¹	Mole fraction of diphenylamine	η (cp)	$E_{vis} \times 10^{-3}$ cal mol ⁻¹
0.0000	0.9661	3.21	0.0000	0.9661	3.21	0.0000	0.9661	3.21
0.1989	0.8716	2.76	0.2000	0.9795	3.88	0.1380	1.0096	3.25
0.4000	0.7889	2.62	0.4000	1.0918	4.55	0.4002	1.3277	4.57
0.5000	0.7334	2.73	0.5000	1.1847	4.58	0.6005	1.6254	6.33
0.5500	0.7227	2.32	0.6000	1.3031	5.24	0.6350 ^e	1.7358	6.73
0.6110 ^e	0.7139	2.46	0.6990 ^e	1.3633	5.69	0.7001	1.7828	6.11
0.6500	0.6934	2.40	0.8000	1.4952	6.58	0.8001	2.0578	6.10
0.7000	0.6809	2.43	1.0000	1.7670	7.38	1.0000	2.5270	6.68
0.8002	0.6409	2.48						
1.0000	0.5903	2.36						

e=eutectic.

Fig. 1. Plot of viscosity vs. composition at 353 K for (1) naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene, (2) naphthalene-diphenylamine, (3) naphthalene-thymol systems.

dotted lines in curves 1 and 3 (Fig. 1). Similar point of inflection at the eutectic concentration was observed in Bi-Sb alloys⁸. Points of inflection at eutectic temperatures have been observed in all the three binary systems. No significant increase or decrease in the viscosities, *i.e.* no point of inflection, has been observed at the eutectic composition of

α -naphthylamine-diphenylamine system⁹. The viscosity at eutectic in naphthalene-diphenyl system¹⁰ possessed a maximum value.

The eutectic mixture of naphthalene-thymol system behaves differently. When naphthalene is added to thymol, the viscosity falls gradually but at the eutectic composition the viscosity decreases instead of increasing (curve 2, Fig. 1). Some workers have also observed a minimum at the eutectic composition in some systems^{2,3,5}. This anomalous behaviour of eutectic melt could not be explained. The deviation in the behaviour of naphthalene-thymol eutectic from the eutectics of other systems is due to thymol. Thymol is highly viscous due to the presence of very strong hydrogen bonding in the liquid state. With the addition of naphthalene to thymol, the hydrogen bonds between the molecules of thymol break effecting the decrease in viscosity. At the eutectic composition, it appears that the clustering effect as observed in the other systems is insignificant. Since the eutectic mixture of naphthalene-thymol system contains a small fraction of naphthalene (0.301 mol), the thermal motion of the molecules does not allow the molecules of naphthalene to come closer and form clusters. In the eutectic melt of this system no other interaction except the breaking of hydrogen bonds seems to occur. The viscosities of pure components and various other mixtures were determined as a function of temperature. The results obey the following equation:

$$\eta = \eta_0 e^{E_{vis}/RT} \quad (1)$$

where η_0 is constant, E_{vis} is activation energy for viscous flow. Fig. 2, 3 and 4 give $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ plots of naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene, naphthalene-diphenylamine and naphthalene-thymol, respectively. The activation energies obtained from these figures are given in Table 1. The activation energy in the naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene shows a decrease upto 0.55 mole fraction of *p*-dichlorobenzene, increases to 2.46×10^{-3} cal mol⁻¹ at the eutectic and decreases again to 2.40×10^{-3} cal mol⁻¹ at 0.65 mole fraction. Furthermore, the activation energy

6.73×10^{-8} , the maximum value, has been found in the eutectic of naphthalene-diphenylamine. A gradual increase in the activation energy of pre-eutectic and decrease in the post-eutectic composition has been observed.

The higher value of viscosity and the activation energies for viscous flow for eutectic melt can be explained on the basis of structural changes occurring in the eutectic liquid, which may be assumed to consist of micro-regions or groups rich in one component or the other. Such grouping of atoms in an ordered array would produce an increase in viscosity and consequently in activation energy. As the temperature of the liquid eutectic is raised, the degree of clustering goes on diminishing. Thus two factors will contribute to the activation energy of the eutectic mixtures: (i) activation energy for viscous flow, and (ii) energy required for breaking the clusters. In case of pure components, no energy is needed for breaking the clusters. Hence, activation energy for pure components should be less than that of their mixtures.

The activation energy and viscosity for the eutectic mixture should be maximum as it contained maximum clusters, eutectic melt being formed at the lowest temperature with definite composition. Also, the activation energy in the case of eutectic should go on decreasing with the rise in temperature as more and more of clusters break. At a temperature, when all the clusters have been broken, only first factor will contribute to E_{vis} .

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ of (I) pure naphthalene, (II) pure *p*-dichlorobenzene, and (III) to (VIII) mixtures with 0.80, 0.70, 0.611 (eutectic), 0.50, 0.40 and 0.20 mole fractions of *p*-dichlorobenzene, respectively.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ of (I) pure diphenylamine, (II) pure naphthalene, and (III) to (VIII) mixtures with 0.80, 0.70, 0.635 (eutectic), 0.60, 0.40 and 0.198 mole fractions of diphenylamine, respectively.

A further evidence for the presence of clusters or microregions rich in one component or the other, comes from the experiments in the centrifuge. The eutectic was centrifuged for one hour so that the clusters get segregated and settled at the bottom of the tube. The melt was chilled and the melting points determined at different distances from the bottom of the tube. They differ from the eutectic temperature showing that the eutectic solid consists of areas rich in one component or the other. This leads to the presence of such regions in the eutectic liquid.

Activation energy shows a steady increase in the naphthalene-thymol system indicating that no microregions in this system are formed.

Determination of interaction in binary system :
The viscosity data can be used to know about the complexing tendency of binary mixtures. The strength of interactions in binary mixtures have been estimated from the expression¹¹:

$$\ln \eta_{mix} = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 \cdot d \quad (2)$$

Fig 4. Plot of $\log \eta$ vs. $1/T$ of (I) pure naphthalene, (II) pure thymol, and (III) to (VIII) mixtures with 0.80, 0.699 (eutectic mixture), 0.60, 0.50, 0.40 and 1.20 mole fractions of thymol, respectively.

where η_{mix} , η_1 and η_2 are experimental viscosities of mixtures, component 1 and component 2, respectively. x_1 and x_2 are the mole fractions of the corresponding components, and d is proportional to W/RT and may be regarded as approximate measure of strength of interaction between the components, W is the interchange energy.

Excess viscosity is given by the following equation :

$$\eta_E = \eta_{mix} - (x_1 \eta_1 + x_2 \eta_2) \quad (3)$$

It was hypothesized^{1,2} that (i) if $\eta_E > 0$ and $d > 0$, then specific interactions would be present ; (ii) if $\eta_E > 0$ and $d < 0$, then weak interactions would be present and (iii) if $\eta_E < 0$ and $d < 0$, then specific interactions would be absent. The values of η_{mix} , η_E and d for the systems naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene, naphthalene-thymol and naphthalene-diphenylamine systems are given in Table 2.

In naphthalene-*p*-dichlorobenzene at eutectic composition $\eta_E < 0$ and $d > 0$ there may be a very

TABLE 2—VISCOSITY OF NAPHTHALENE CONTAINING BINARY MIXTURES AT 353 K

Mole fraction of components B	η_{mix} cp	η_E cp	d
Naphthalene (A)- <i>p</i> -dichlorobenzene (B) system			
0.200	0.8716	0.0045	0.0863
0.400	0.7889	-0.0157	0.0247
0.500	0.7334	-0.0355	-0.0790
0.550	0.7227	-0.0283	-0.0434
0.611 ^e	0.7139	-0.0153	0.0227
0.650	0.6934	-0.0219	-0.0217
0.700	0.6809	-0.0166	0.0041
0.800	0.6498	-0.0119	0.0074
Naphthalene (A)-thymol (B) system			
0.200	0.9795	-0.1320	-0.5713
0.400	1.0918	-0.1835	-0.4474
0.500	1.1847	-0.1726	-0.3518
0.600	1.3031	-0.3981	-0.2306
0.699 ^e	1.3633	-0.1574	-0.3458
0.800	1.4952	-0.1079	-0.2657
Naphthalene (A)-diphenylamine (B) system			
0.138	1.0096	-0.1559	0.0425
0.400	1.3277	-0.2516	-0.2311
0.600	1.6254	-0.2698	-0.2043
0.635 ^e	1.7358	-0.2146	-0.0756
0.700	1.7828	-0.2703	-0.2687
0.800	2.0578	-0.1533	-0.0620

^e = eutectic.

weak interaction at this composition, whereas near the eutectic composition $\eta_E < 0$ and $d < 0$, there may not be any interaction in these mixtures. In naphthalene-diphenylamine system although $\eta_E < 0$ and $d < 0$, there is a marked increase in the magnitude of η_E and d at eutectic composition suggesting the presence of weak interactions. Similar observations are made in case of the other system. These weak interactions may be due to the formation of micro-regions in the eutectic melt.

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